

Procyanidin and Its Benefits on Aging: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Procyanidin is an oligomeric compound composed of catechin and epicatechin. Procyanidin can be found in many foods that can be found easily in Indonesia. In contrast, many people might not know that procyanidin can be found innatural plantations like fruits and cultivation crops. It can be found in grapes, apples, cranberries, cherries, strawberries, kiwis, apricots, and mangoes. Also in barley, sorghum, red rice, soybeans, and cocoa. Even nuts like almonds, hazelnuts, and peanuts. Many studies found that it has medicinal properties. Famous for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, procyanidin also has many other benefits. Aging is a definite process. It cannot be stopped. Lately, researchers have been trying to slow the process of aging. This literature review discusses the benefits of procyanidin for aging.

KEYWORDS: procyanidin, polyphenol, aging, osteoporosis, cardioprotective, neuroprotective, chondroprotective

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INTRODUCTION

Procyanidin is an oligomeric compound composed of catechin and epicatechin monomers. It could be found in foods and can have significant medicinal properties. Although much is already known about their biological activities, research concerning their medicinal benefits is continuing (1).

People are living longer, and the number of older in the population is growing. As people age, their bodies experience some changes. There are many health problems associated with aging, which attracts health researchers to investigate large natural compounds to prevent aging.

Procyanidins are promising in the treatment of chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, as they prevent cell damage related to oxidative stress. Therefore, it is necessary to study the advantages of procyanidins in aging. In this review, advances in the mechanisms of procyanidins on aging prevention were presented, which includes its activity on antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, cardioprotection, neuroprotection, generative disorder, hormonal, and muscle strength (2).

MAIN BODY

Procyanidin

Polyphenols can be found naturally in medicinal plants and food (2), and they can be found in plant-based food products (3). Procyanidin, known as condensed tannins, is derived from proanthocyanidin(2). Procyanidin is a naturally found polyphenol composed of flavan-3-ol units, epicatechins, and catechins. They can be classified as polymers or oligomers according to their degree of polymerization. It is found in fruits, vegetables, grains, legumes, leaves, tea, coffee, wine, chocolate, and cereal. Some fruits rich in procyanidin are blueberries, strawberries, grapes, apples, kiwis, cherries, cranberries, apricot, and mangoes. It also can be found in pears and bananas. Chocolate, cocoa powder, barley, sorghum, red rice, and soybeans are also rich in procyanidin. (2–4).

Antioxidant

Aging is an unavoidable process that affects all populations and results in the development of diseases and leads to death. Oxidative stress is a primary cause of cellular injury, even in normal physiological conditions. Several antioxidants have been studied to discover their beneficial effect against

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oxidative stress, including flavonoids and polyphenols (5). Procyanidins have been endorsed to possess significant antioxidant capacities. It scavenges free radicals through a robust inhibitory effect against lipid oxidation (6). Procyanidins also maintain a normal cell cycle and regulate the antioxidant enzyme system by protecting macrophages against oxidative stress produced by H₂O₂, inhibiting intracellular ROS production by reducing the chelated metal ions, and inducing the overexpression of antioxidant enzymes (7–11). Oligomeric procyanidins also presented antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacteria and *Candida albicans* due to their high antioxidant capacity (9). The antioxidant effects of cocoa polyphenols are more evident in people with physical conditions or a significant antioxidant deficiency (12). However, the effects of procyanidins are dose-dependent and organ-dependent (8,13). Furthermore, Tapari reported that the procyanidin-rich extract of natural cocoa powder could elevate intracellular ROS levels. This prooxidant effect was beneficial as it could diminish the invasive potential of epithelial ovarian cancer cells (14).

Generative disorder:

- Neuroprotective

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is an age-related and progressive neurodegenerative disease with memory impairment in later life. AD is diagnosed by accumulation of amyloid, observed as a deposition in the cerebral cortex and hippocampus, called a senile plaque, composed of amyloid β -proteins. A study using procyanidin extracted from apples found that it inhibited amyloid β -proteins aggregation and neurotoxicity (15). Two mechanisms contributing to Alzheimer's disease pathogenesis are neuroinflammation and oxidative stress. A recent study using *Chrysophyllum perpulchrum* extract reported restoring spatial learning deficits and recognition memory. It also reduces oxidative stress status in the brain. Using the extract containing procyanidin P2 and P3, the study reported an approximately 3-fold decrease of NO level in different brain areas, suggesting its repressive action on the A β -induced iNOS activity and the release of cytokine via downregulation of NF- κ B expression. It also reported a reduction of activated microglia in hippocampal and CPF areas (16).

Parkinson's disease (PD) is an irreversible degenerative disorder caused by the premature death of dopaminergic neurons and dopamine deficiency in the nigrostriatal system. Some symptoms are tremors, rigidity, postural instability, and slow voluntary movement. Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) are a type of serine/threonine protein kinases consisting of the extracellular, signal-regulated kinase (Erk) 1 and 2 (Erk1/2), P38 isoforms, and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK). Research suggests that abnormal regulation of MAPKs may contribute to the pathogenesis of PD. Using cinnamon procyanidin oligomers (CPOs) was reported to have a neuroprotection effect against 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP⁺)-induced

cytotoxicity. It was found to activate Erk1/2 phosphorylation, attenuate an intracellular level of reactive oxygen species, enhance the ratio of Bcl-2/Bax expression and inhibit caspase-3 activity (17). Another study found that proanthocyanidin (PC) prevented mitochondrial apoptosis, reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, and c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) activation in neurons. It reported that PC could reduce cell apoptosis in vitro and inhibit striatal dopamine depletion in vivo (18).

Grapeseed procyanidin (GSP) was reported to have a potential protective effect on cognitive dysfunction in mice. Procyanidin has a strong antioxidant effect and stabilizes NR2B/CREB pathway, which is essential for memory processes and formation. GSP enhanced antioxidant enzyme activities, increasing superoxide dismutase (SOD) total activity. Superoxide dismutase can scavenge free radicals (19). In another setting, an ethanol-induced hippocampal neuronal toxicity, grapeseed procyanidin was also reported to increase superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity and decrease the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). GSP also increases the number of dendrites and total dendritic length per cell (20). Another study found that procyanidin has neuroprotective effects via activating the nuclear factor-erythroid 2-related factor 2/antioxidant response element (Nrf2/ARE) pathway. It improved the levels of antioxidant enzymes, including glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD) but decreased the levels of ROS and MDA (21). A study using procyanidin B2 found that it has neuroprotective effects in the primary culture of rat cerebellar granule neurons. It protects from oxidative and nitrosative stressors and glutamate-induced endotoxicity (22).

- Chondroprotective

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a degenerative disorder of the joints that causes significant pain and functional disability. OA involves the articular cartilage, subchondral bone, ligaments, synovial membrane, and periarticular muscle. The cause of OA is unknown, but some studies have suggested that it results from the combination of biochemical factors and mechanical stress, mainly reactive oxygen species (ROS) and matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) (23).

Grapeseed proanthocyanidin extract (GSPE) has an antioxidant effect, decreasing the chondrocyte damage and proteoglycan loss by scavenging ROS and MMPs. It also reduced MMP-13-producing cells in arthritic joints. The antioxidant activity of GSPE also decreases nitrotyrosine production in cartilage and synovium; it may contribute to the antinociceptive effect. GSPE also has anti-inflammatory activity by reducing synovial inflammation (synovitis) and suppressing osteoclastogenesis (23).

Proanthocyanidin from red jasmine rice crude has also shown chondroprotective potential. It inhibited the IL-1 β -induced NF- κ B activation signaling pathway, resulting in the reduction of proinflammatory cascades and thus the production of cartilage-degrading enzymes (24).

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An olive-grape seed extract containing hydroxytyrosol and procyanidins was found to exert anti-IL-1 β effects in chondrocytes in vitro. It also reduces the severity of post-traumatic OA in mice and rabbit models (25). In another study using human articular chondrocytes cultures, both in vitro and ex vivo, hydroxytyrosol and procyanidins showed anti-IL-1 β activities (26).

Extract of *Croton palanostigma* was riched in proanthocyanidins, has antioxidant activity, and prevents the catabolic breakdown of the human cartilage matrix. Its chondroprotective actions are associated with direct inhibition of MMP activity and enhanced chondrocyte expression and production of IGF-1 (Insulin-like Growth Factor), an anabolic growth factor known for cartilage repair (27). Procyanidin was also found to suppress VEGF-mediated signaling (Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor) in OA chondrocytes by reducing phosphorylation of VEGF-receptor 2 in human OA primary chondrocytes (28)

Apple procyanidin (procyanidin B2) was found to protect against articular cartilage degeneration and prevent the development of knee osteoarthritis in mice because of the modulation of mitochondrial biogenesis and proteoglycan biosynthesis in chondrocytes (29).

Cardioprotective

Several studies have shown the cardioprotective effects of procyanidins. Possible beneficial effects on cardiovascular include vasodilators, anti-inflammation, anti-thrombotic, and anti-atherogenic.

Vasodilation: vasodilation is beneficial in angina and hypertension (30). Procyanidins increase NO synthesis (31) and induce endothelium-dependent vasodilatation (32), resulting in reducing heart rate (33), thus reducing systolic and diastolic blood pressure (34,35). Some studies showed that dietary intake of procyanidins was significantly associated with reducing renin and Angiotensin II plasma levels and the risk of hypertension induced by a high-fat diet (36,37). Another study also reported that low-dose procyanidins (<245 mg/day) could significantly reduce SBP, DBP, PP, and MAP, while no significant effect was reported on the higher dose (38).

Antioxidant: Procyanidins improve antioxidant defenses (34) and decrease oxidative stress in endothelial cells (39).

Anti-inflammation: Procyanidins alleviate inflammatory responses (34), decrease NF-kB activation, decrease COX, LPO, and monocyte adhesion, and attenuate proinflammatory cytokines and chemocytokines release (31).

Anti-thrombotic: Procyanidins suppressed platelet aggregation (33), increased PGI₂, and decreased TXA₂ (31).

Anti-atherogenic: anthocyanin-rich extract supplementation affected the expression of genes involved in essential processes underlying atherosclerosis (40). Procyanidins work in the regulation of lipid metabolism (41) by significantly decreasing total cholesterol, LDL-C, and triglycerides and increasing HDL levels with four weeks of

flavanol-rich treatment (13,42). Moreover, it blocks the oxidation of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) (34), improves endothelial function, improves antioxidant defenses, alleviates inflammatory responses (43), and protects VSMCs against oxidative stress and apoptosis (44). In 2018, Rong, in his study using ApoE-KO mice fed with a western-type diet, showed procyanidins intake could alleviate the lipid disorder and ameliorate atherosclerosis via regulating gene expression involved in hepatic lipid homeostasis effectively (45).

Lately, Dalgaard found that the inverse association between flavonoid intake and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease was more potent in current smokers and individuals who consume high quantities of alcohol (46).

In conclusion, many studies above show that procyanidins treatment was dose and time-dependent.

Osteoporosis

Bone diseases are caused by disharmony in the bone remodeling process, which is mediated by bone-formative osteoblasts and bone-resorbing osteoclasts. Excessive activation of osteoclasts leads to excessive bone destruction. It is associated with low concentration levels of estrogen in postmenopausal women or excessive inflammatory responses in pathological circumstances (47). Osteoporosis is characterized by an increased bone turnover with insufficient bone formation relative to bone resorption, leading to increased bone fragility and increased risk of fracture (48)

Many studies found that procyanidin can attenuate bone loss. Using Grape Seed Proanthocyanidin Extract (GSPE), Tofani et al. in 2004, found that GSPE induces bone formation in low-calcium feeding rats. The effects were more significant in trabecular bone than cortical bone (49). Di et al. also reported that GSPE promotes proliferation and inhibits osteoclast differentiation and apoptosis in vitro. It also protects against lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced inflammatory bone loss in vivo. (47) Another study in 2014 using GSPE found that proanthocyanidins protect MC3T3-E1 osteoblastic cells from H₂O₂-induced mitochondrial dysfunction and apoptosis by improving mitochondrial function and inhibiting mitochondrial dysfunction and inhibiting the activation of p53 signaling (48).

Orsolic et al. in 2018 reported that proanthocyanidin demonstrated a significant antioxidant and antiosteoporotic effect in retinoic acid-induced osteoporotic rats. It maintains calcium and phosphorus homeostasis and increases antioxidative enzymes that increase bone markers formation and mineral density while reducing lipid peroxidation. Proanthocyanidins also inhibit the production of proinflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α and IL-1 β (50). Chen et al. reported that proanthocyanidin protected osteoblasts against dexamethasone-induced oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and osteogenic impairment by activating the antioxidant Nrf2 pathway. It subsequently decreased ROS accumulation and mitochondrial superoxide levels in osteoblasts (51). Supporting the previous study, Tenkumo et al. also reported that proanthocyanidin could

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prevent bone loss and facilitate bone healing in ovariectomized animals due to its antioxidative and anti-inflammatory properties. (52)

Muscle Strength

Low muscle strength is associated with mortality, presumably due to low muscle mass (sarcopenia) and physical inactivity. Sarcopenia is the loss of muscle mass that occurs with aging (53). A study on 32-week-old senescence-accelerated mice which supplemented a diet containing procyanidins improves mitochondrial quality via regulating molecular signals involved in mitochondrial biogenesis, mitochondrial fusion and fission, and autophagic flux. Optimized mitochondrial quality by oligonol led to a positive protein turnover via increased muscle protein synthesis, decreased muscle protein degradation, and mitochondria-mediated apoptosis (54). Furthermore, five consecutive weeks of administration of dark chocolate mixture (mainly containing procyanidins) to obese middle-aged mice showed 2.38 times increase in body weight and significantly improved physical performance evaluated with the hang-wire, inverted-screen, weight-lifting tests, and dynamometry compared with the performance of the controls consistent with the modulation of the muscle biomarkers for sarcopenia (55).

Hormone Regulation

As most of the population ages, hormonal issues such as osteoporosis, insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome, and hormonal-related cancer become medical attention. The use of alternative and complementary products is rapidly expanding (56). Procyanidins were one of the most likely compounds found in fruit and vegetable. One of the procyanidins' benefits is on preventing bone aging. A study on 43 postmenopausal women with osteopenia receiving standardized procyanidins supplementation for 12 weeks showed a beneficial effect through improving the antioxidant defense system in the plasma and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) that was accompanied by an increase in indicators of bone marrow (57).

Procyanidins also have some roles in improving insulin resistance. As we know, α -Glucosidase is a critical enzyme in the human intestine. Inhibiting its activity can lower blood sugar levels to prevent hyperglycemia-induced tissue damage. Procyanidins intervene in the progression of type-2 diabetes by inhibiting α -glucosidase. A study on different structures of procyanidins showed that the α -glucosidase was lower than that of acarbose. A-type procyanidins might have better inhibitory activity than B-type procyanidins (58).

Moreover, the study of polyphenol-enriched cocoa extract administration on insulin-resistant rats showed sucrose-induced insulin resistance, hepatic carbohydrate and lipid dysmetabolism, oxidative stress, and inflammation were effectively disrupted. Dietary administration of cocoa flavanols (mainly containing procyanidins) may effectively

prevent or reverse prediabetes (59). Furthermore, Montagut, in his *in vitro* study, showed that grape seed procyanidins extract (GSPE) differed from insulin in how it stimulated glucose uptake in insulin-resistant adipocytes. This suggests that GSPE is partly dependent on Irs1 when stimulating glucose uptake but also suggests that GSPE has a direct effect on Glut4 transporter activity. These mechanisms could be responsible for slightly improving plasma IR parameters (mainly by reducing insulinemia) (60). A study on *streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats* showed that procyanidins mimic and influence insulin effects by directly acting on specific components of the insulin-signaling transduction pathway (61). Kawakami stated that ingestion of 25 g of cacao polyphenol-rich chocolate before a 50 g OGTT could enhance early insulin and GLP-1 secretion in healthy participants and illustrates the potential of cacao polyphenol-rich chocolate in managing postprandial glucose excursions (62). Castell-Auvi, in his *in vivo* experiment, reported that different doses of procyanidins affected insulinemia in different ways by modifying β -cell functionality and insulin degradation. In addition, insulin gene expression, insulin synthesis, and expression of genes related to insulin secretion were all down-regulated. *In vitro* studies revealed that GSPE decreased the ability of β -cells to secrete insulin in response to glucose. GSPE increased glucose uptake in β -cells under high-glucose conditions, but impaired glucose-induced mitochondrial hyperpolarization decreased adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and altered cellular membrane potentials. GSPE also modified Glut2, glucokinase, and Ucp2 gene expression and altered the expression of hepatic insulin-degrading enzyme (Ide), thereby altering insulin degradation (63).

Cocoa flavanols which are rich in procyanidins, appear to alleviate metabolic syndrome, and specifically, derangements in glucose homeostasis, by several mechanisms: cocoa may reduce glucose excursion after a meal by inhibiting digestive enzymes, inhibiting glucose transporters, and promoting an incretin response (64).

Rosenberg et al. reported the effect of natural products on steroid hormone-regulated gene expression. Procyanidin extracts exhibited weak estrogenic and progestin activity but only at the highest concentrations tested. This has been demonstrated to have antiproliferative and anticarcinogenic activities in cell culture and animal studies (56).

Cell senescence

Aging is an inevitable process that causes functional decline progressively in organisms. (65). Several studies reported that procyanidin has anti-aging effects. In degenerative retinal disorders, GSPE was reported to improve impaired mitochondrial function in the aging retinal pigment epithelium, increasing NAMPT expression and improving NAD⁺ contents in aging mice via NAMPT/SIRT1/NLRP3 pathway. NAD⁺ promotes SIRT1 expression and then inhibits the activation of the inflammasome complex. (66).

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Previous study in 2008 using persimmon peel also reported that proanthocyanidin elevated SIRT1 expression and decreased oxidative DNA adducts, 8-Hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8OH-dG) (67). In a recent study, procyanidin C1 was reported to be a broad-spectrum senolytic compound. It also can act as a xenomorphic agent, minimizing senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP) expression in lower concentrations (65).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Procyanidin, an oligomeric compound composed of catechin and epicatechin, can be found in many foods in Indonesia. Many studies found that it can be beneficial for the human body. While aging cannot be stopped, we can try to slow the process of aging using procyanidin.

Competing Interest

The authors declare that there are no competing interests related to the study.

REFERENCES

- I. Rue EA, Rush MD, van Breemen RB. Procyanidins: a comprehensive review encompassing structure elucidation via mass spectrometry. *Phytochem Rev* [Internet]. 2018 Feb;17(1):1–16. Available from: <https://europepmc.org/articles/PMC5891158>
- II. Yang H, Tuo X, Wang L, Tundis R, Portillo MP, Simal-Gandara J, et al. Bioactive procyanidins from dietary sources: The relationship between bioactivity and polymerization degree. *Trends Food Sci Technol* [Internet]. 2021;111:114–27. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2021.02.063>
- III. Dasiman R, Nor NM, Eshak Z, Mutalip SSM, Suwandi NR, Bidin H. A review of procyanidin: Updates on current bioactivities and potential health benefits. Vol. 12, *Biointerface Research in Applied Chemistry*. AMG Transcend Association; 2022. p. 5918–40.
- IV. Zhu Y, Yuen M, Li W, Yuen H, Wang M, Smith D, et al. Composition analysis and antioxidant activity evaluation of a high purity oligomeric procyanidin prepared from sea buckthorn by a green method. *Curr Res Food Sci* [Internet]. 2021;4(November):840–51. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crfs.2021.11.008>
- V. Pizzino G, Irrera N, Cucinotta M, Pallio G, Mannino F, Arcoraci V, et al. Oxidative Stress: Harms and Benefits for Human Health. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2017;2017:8416763.
- VI. Harlen WC, Jati IRAP. Antioxidant activity of anthocyanins in common legume grains. 2nd ed. *Polyphenols: Mechanisms of Action in Human Health and Disease*. Elsevier Inc.; 2018. 81–92 p.
- VII. Yan F, Chen L, Chen W, Zhao L, Lu Q, Liu R. Protective effect of procyanidin A-type dimers against H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress in prostate DU145 cells through the MAPKs signaling pathway. *Life Sci*. 2021;266(August 2020):118908.
- VIII. Castrillejo VM, Romero MM, Esteve M, Ardévol A, Blay M, Bladé C, et al. Antioxidant effects of a grape seed procyanidin extract and oleoyl-estrone in obese Zucker rats. *Nutrition*. 2011;27(11–12):1172–6.
- IX. Martins GR, do Amaral FRL, Brum FL, Mohana-Borges R, de Moura SST, Ferreira FA, et al. Chemical characterization, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of açai seed (*Euterpe oleracea* Mart.) extracts containing A- and B-type procyanidins. *Lwt*. 2020;132(June):1–11.
- X. Xu HY, Feng XH, Zhao PF, Damirin A, Ma CM. Procyanidin A2 penetrates L-02 cells and protects against tert-butyl hydroperoxide-induced oxidative stress by activating Nrf2 through JNK and p38 phosphorylation. *J Funct Foods*. 2019;62(March):103562.
- XI. Maleki M, Khelghati N, Alemi F, Bazdar M, Asemi Z, Majidinia M, et al. Stabilization of telomere by the antioxidant property of polyphenols: Anti-aging potential. *Life Sci*. 2020;259(August):118341.
- XII. Allgrove JE, Davison G. Chocolate/cocoa polyphenols and oxidative stress. 2nd ed. *Polyphenols: Mechanisms of Action in Human Health and Disease*. Elsevier Inc.; 2018. 207–219 p.
- XIII. Davinelli S, Corbi G, Zarrelli A, Arisi M, Calzavara-Pinton P, Grassi D, et al. Short-term supplementation with flavanol-rich cocoa improves lipid profile, antioxidant status and positively influences the AA/EPA ratio in healthy subjects. *J Nutr Biochem*. 2018;61:33–9.
- XIV. Taparia SS, Khanna A. Procyanidin-rich extract of natural cocoa powder causes ROS-mediated caspase-3 dependent apoptosis and reduction of pro-MMP-2 in epithelial ovarian carcinoma cell lines. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2016;83:130–40.
- XV. Toda T, Sunagawa T, Kanda T, Tagashira M, Shirasawa T, Shimizu T. Apple Procyanidins Suppress Amyloid β -Protein Aggregation. *Biochem Res Int*. 2011;2011.
- XVI. Go PKN, Touhami O, Ahami A, Hessni A El. Neuroprotective effects of the *Chrysophyllum perpulchrum* extract against an Alzheimer-like rat model of β amyloid 1 - 40 intrahippocampal injection. *Transl Neurosci*. 2021;545–60.
- XVII. Xu Q, Chen Z, Zhu B, Li Y, Reddy MB, Liu H, et al. Neuroprotective effects of b-type cinnamon procyanidin oligomers on mpp+-induced apoptosis in a cell culture model of parkinson's disease. *Molecules*. 2021;26(21).
- XVIII. Chen H, Xu J, Lv Y, He P, Liu C, Jiao J, et al. Proanthocyanidins exert a neuroprotective effect via

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- ROS/JNK signaling in MPTP-induced Parkinson's disease models in vitro and in vivo. *Mol Med Rep.* 2018;18(6):4913–21.
- XIX. Gong X, Xu L, Fang X, Zhao X, Du Y, Wu H, et al. Protective effects of grape seed procyanidin on isoflurane-induced cognitive impairment in mice. *Pharm Biol [Internet].* 2020;58(1):200–7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13880209.2020.1730913>
- XX. Jin W, Sun M, Yuan B, Wang R, Yan H, Qiao X. Neuroprotective Effects of Grape Seed Procyanidins on Ethanol-Induced Injury and Oxidative Stress in Rat Hippocampal Neurons. *Alcohol Alcohol.* 2020;55(4):357–66.
- XXI. Chen J, Chen Y, Zheng Y, Zhao J, Yu H, Zhu J, et al. Neuroprotective Effects and Mechanisms of Procyanidins In Vitro and In Vivo. *Molecules [Internet].* 2021;26(10). Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/1420-3049/26/10/2963>
- XXII. Sutcliffe TC, Winter AN, Punessen NC, Linseman DA. Procyanidin B2 protects neurons from oxidative, nitrosative, and excitotoxic stress. *Antioxidants.* 2017;6(4).
- XXIII. Woo YJ, Joo Y Bin, Jung YO, Ju JH, la Cho M, Oh HJ, et al. Grape seed proanthocyanidin extract ameliorates monosodium iodoacetate induced osteoarthritis. *Exp Mol Med.* 2011;43(10):561–70.
- XXIV. Thonghoi S, Jaitham R, Kongdang P, Yodkeeree S. Red jasmine rice extract suppresses genes associated with cartilage degradation in IL-1 β -stimulated chondro- sarcoma (SW1353) via blocking NF- κ B pathway. 2017;(2).
- XXV. Mével E, Merceron C, Vinatier C, Krisa S, Richard T, Masson M, et al. Olive and grape seed extract prevents post-Traumatic osteoarthritis damages and exhibits in vitro anti IL-1 β activities before and after oral consumption. *Sci Rep [Internet].* 2016;6:0–14. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/srep33527>
- XXVI. Wauquier F, Mevel E, Krisa S, Richard T, Valls J, Hornedo-Ortega R, et al. Chondroprotective properties of human-enriched serum following polyphenol extract absorption: Results from an exploratory clinical trial. *Nutrients.* 2019;11(12).
- XXVII. Miller MJS, Bobrowski P, Shukla M, Gupta K, Haqqi TM. Chondroprotective effects of a proanthocyanidin rich Amazonian genonutrient reflects direct inhibition of matrix metalloproteinases and upregulation of IGF-1 production by human chondrocytes. *J Inflamm.* 2007;4:1–10.
- XXVIII. Wang A, Leong DJ, He Z, Xu L, Liu L, Kim SJ, et al. Procyanidins mitigate osteoarthritis pathogenesis by, at least in part, suppressing vascular endothelial growth factor signaling. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2016;17(12).
- XXIX. Masuda I, Koike M, Nakashima S, Mizutani Y, Ozawa Y, Watanabe K, et al. Apple procyanidins promote mitochondrial biogenesis and proteoglycan biosynthesis in chondrocytes. *Sci Rep [Internet].* 2018;8(1):1–13. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-25348-1>
- XXX. Fusi F, Trezza A, Tramaglino M, Sgaragli G, Saponara S, Spiga O. The beneficial health effects of flavonoids on the cardiovascular system: Focus on K⁺ channels. *Pharmacol Res.* 2020;152(October 2019):104625.
- XXXI. Quiñones M, Miguel M, Aleixandre A. Beneficial effects of polyphenols on cardiovascular disease. *Pharmacol Res.* 2013;68(1):125–31.
- XXXII. Khan NQ, Patel B, Kang SS, Dhariwal SK, Husain F, Wood EG, et al. regulation of vascular endothelial function by red wine procyanidins: Implications for cardiovascular health. *Tetrahedron.* 2015;71(20):3059–65.
- XXXIII. Rull G, Mohd-Zain ZN, Shiel J, Lundberg MH, Collier DJ, Johnston A, et al. Effects of high flavanol dark chocolate on cardiovascular function and platelet aggregation. *Vascul Pharmacol.* 2015;71:70–8.
- XXXIV. Behl T, Bungau S, Kumar K, Zengin G, Khan F, Kumar A, et al. Pleotropic Effects of Polyphenols in Cardiovascular System. *Biomed Pharmacother.* 2020;130:110714.
- XXXV. Quiñones M, Guerrero L, Suarez M, Pons Z, Aleixandre A, Arola L, et al. Low-molecular procyanidin rich grape seed extract exerts an antihypertensive effect in males spontaneously hypertensive rats. *Food Res Int.* 2013;51(2):587–95.
- XXXVI. Santos IB, de Bem GF, da Costa CA, de Carvalho LCRM, de Medeiros AF, Silva DLB, et al. Açai seed extract prevents the renin-angiotensin system activation, oxidative stress and inflammation in white adipose tissue of high-fat diet-fed mice. *Nutr Res.* 2020;79:35–49.
- XXXVII. Godos J, Vitale M, Micek A, Ray S, Martini D, Del Rio D, et al. Dietary polyphenol intake, blood pressure, and hypertension: A systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Antioxidants.* 2019;8(6):1–21.
- XXXVIII. Ren J, An J, Chen M, Yang H, Ma Y. Effect of proanthocyanidins on blood pressure: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Pharmacol Res.* 2021;165:105329.
- XXXIX. Hort MA, Straliootto MR, Duz MS, Netto PM, Souza CB, Schulz T, et al. Cardioprotective effects of a proanthocyanidin-rich fraction from *Croton celtidifolius* Baill: Focus on atherosclerosis. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2012;50(10):3769–75.
- XL. Mauray A, Felgines C, Morand C, Mazur A, Scalbert A, Milenkovic D. Bilberry anthocyanin-

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- rich extract alters expression of genes related to atherosclerosis development in aorta of apo E-deficient mice. *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis*. 2012;22(1):72–80.
- XLII. Fried R. The Polyphenolic Antioxidant Resveratrol, the Carotenoid Lycopene, and the Proanthocyanidin Pycnogenol. *Erectile Dysfunction As a Cardiovascular Impairment*. Elsevier Inc.; 2014. 259–291 p.
- XLIII. Nie X, Tang W, Zhang Z, Yang C, Qian L, Xie X, et al. Procyanidin B2 mitigates endothelial endoplasmic reticulum stress through a PPAR δ -Dependent mechanism. *Redox Biol* [Internet]. 2020;37:101728. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.redox.2020.101728>
- XLIV. Zhang LM, Lv SS, Fu SR, Wang JQ, Liang LY, Li RQ, et al. Procyanidins inhibit fine particulate matter-induced vascular smooth muscle cells apoptosis via the activation of the Nrf2 signaling pathway. *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf*. 2021;223:112586.
- XLV. Rong S, Zhao S, Kai X, Zhang L, Zhao Y, Xiao X, et al. Procyanidins extracted from the litchi pericarp attenuate atherosclerosis and hyperlipidemia associated with consumption of a high fat diet in apolipoprotein-E knockout mice. *Biomed Pharmacother*. 2018;97(October 2017):1639–44.
- XLVI. Dalgaard F, Bondonno NP, Murray K, Bondonno CP, Lewis JR, Croft KD, et al. Associations between habitual flavonoid intake and hospital admissions for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Planet Heal*. 2019;3(11):e450–9.
- XLVII. Kwak SC, Cheon YH, Lee CH, Jun HY, Yoon KH, Lee MS, et al. Grape seed proanthocyanidin extract prevents bone loss via regulation of osteoclast differentiation, apoptosis, and proliferation. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(10):1–14.
- XLVIII. Zhang Z, Zheng L, Zhao Z, Shi J, Wang X, Huang J. Grape seed proanthocyanidins inhibit H₂O₂-induced osteoblastic MC3T3-E1 cell apoptosis via ameliorating H₂O₂-induced mitochondrial dysfunction. *J Toxicol Sci*. 2014;39(5):803–13.
- XLIX. Tofani I, Maki K, Kojima K, Kimura M. Beneficial effects of grape seed proanthocyanidins extract on the formation of tibia bone in low-calcium feeding rats. *Pediatr Dent J*. 2004;14(1):47–53.
- L. Oršolić N, Nemrava J, Jeleč Ž, Kukulj M, Odeh D, Terzić S, et al. The beneficial effect of proanthocyanidins and icariin on biochemical markers of bone turnover in rats. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2018;19(9):2746.
- LI. Chen L, Hu SL, Xie J, Yan DY, Weng SJ, Tang JH, et al. Proanthocyanidins-Mediated Nrf2 Activation Ameliorates Glucocorticoid-Induced Oxidative Stress and Mitochondrial Dysfunction in Osteoblasts. *Oxid Med Cell Longev*. 2020;2020.
- LII. Tenkumo T, Aobulikasimu A, Asou Y, Shirato M. Proanthocyanidin-rich grape seed extract improves bone loss, bone healing, and implant osseointegration in ovariectomized animals. *Sci Rep* [Internet]. 2020;1–14. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-65403-4>
- LIII. Kalyani RR, Corriere M, Ferrucci L. Age-related and disease-related muscle loss: The effect of diabetes, obesity, and other diseases. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2014;2(10):819–29.
- LIV. Chang YC, Chen YT, Liu HW, Chan YC, Liu MY, Hu SH, et al. Oligonol Alleviates Sarcopenia by Regulation of Signaling Pathways Involved in Protein Turnover and Mitochondrial Quality. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. 2019;63(10):1–9.
- LV. Munguia L, Ramirez-sanchez I, Meaney E, Villarreal F, Ceballos G, Najera N. Food Bioscience Flavonoids from dark chocolate and (–)-epicatechin ameliorate high-fat diet-induced decreases in mobility and muscle damage in aging mice. *Food Biosci*. 2020;37(August):100710.
- LVI. Rosenberg Zand RS, Jenkins DJA, Diamandis EP. Effects of natural products and nutraceuticals on steroid hormone-regulated gene expression. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2001;312(1–2):213–9.
- LVII. Majidi Z, Ansari M, Maghbooli Z, Ghasemi A, Ebrahimi SSS, Hossein-nezhad A, et al. Oligopin® Supplementation Mitigates Oxidative Stress in Postmenopausal Women with Osteopenia: A Randomized, Double-blind, Placebo-Controlled Trial. *Phytomedicine*. 2021;81(October 2020):153417.
- LVIII. Zhao L, Wen L, Lu Q, Liu R. Interaction mechanism between α -glucosidase and A-type trimer procyanidin revealed by integrated spectroscopic analysis techniques. *Int J Biol Macromol*. 2020;143:173–80.
- LIX. Castro MC, Villagarcía H, Nazar A, Arbeláez LG, Massa ML, Del Zotto H, et al. cacao extract enriched in polyphenols prevents endocrine-metabolic disturbances in a rat model of prediabetes triggered by a sucrose rich diet. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2020;247(September 2019):112263.
- LX. Montagut G, Bladé C, Blay M, Fernández-Larrea J, Pujadas G, Salvadó MJ, et al. Effects of a grape seed procyanidin extract (GSPE) on insulin resistance. *J*

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- Nutr Biochem. 2010;21(10):961–7.
- LXI. Pinent M, Blay M, Bladé MC, Salvadó MJ, Arola L, Ardévol A. Grape seed-derived procyanidins have an antihyperglycemic effect in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats and insulinomimetic activity in insulin-sensitive cell lines. *Endocrinology*. 2004;145(11):4985–90.
- LXII. Kawakami Y, Watanabe Y, Mazuka M, Yagi N, Sawazaki A, Koganei M, et al. Effect of cacao polyphenol-rich chocolate on postprandial glycemia, insulin, and incretin secretion in healthy participants. *Nutrition*. 2021;85:111128.
- LXIII. Castell-Auví A, Cedó L, Pallarès V, Blay MT, Pinent M, Motilva MJ, et al. Procyanidins modify insulinemia by affecting insulin production and degradation. *J Nutr Biochem*. 2012;23(12):1565–72.
- LXIV. Strat KM, Rowley TJ, Smithson AT, Tessem JS, Hulver MW, Liu D, et al. Mechanisms by which cocoa flavanols improve metabolic syndrome and related disorders. *J Nutr Biochem*. 2016;35:1–21.
- LXV. Xu Q, Fu Q, Li Z, Liu H, Wang Y, Lin X, et al. The flavonoid procyanidin C1 has senotherapeutic activity and increases lifespan in mice. *Nat Metab*. 2021;3(12):1706–26.
- LXVI. Wan W, Zhu W, Wu Y, Long Y, Liu H, Wan W, et al. Grape seed proanthocyanidin extract moderated retinal pigment epithelium cellular senescence through nampt/sirt1/NLRP3 pathway. *J Inflamm Res*. 2021;14:3129–43.
- LXVII. Lee YA, Cho EJ, Yokozawa T. Protective effect of persimmon (*Diospyros kaki*) peel proanthocyanidin against oxidative damage under H₂O₂-induced cellular senescence. *Biol Pharm Bull*. 2008;31(6):1265–9.